

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE EVALUATION PROCESS TO INCREASE THE PERFORMANCE OF HUMAN RESOURCES: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract

Purpose - aims to provide an overview of the importance of the evaluation process for increasing the performance of human resources, detailing the benefits it brings to individuals and organizations alike.

Methodology/approach – a qualitative research approach will be conducted focusing on the review of the existing literature on performance evaluation process, human resources management, and organizational performance.

Findings – would emphasize the multifaceted benefits of the evaluation process, illustrating how it not only enhances individual performance but also contributes to broader organizational success and a positive workplace culture.

Research limitations/implications – can derive from the subjectivity of the evaluation as performance evaluations can be influenced by the biases of the evaluators (internal factors). On the other hand, uncontrolled external factors, such as economic conditions or organization changes, can influence employee performance independently of the evaluation process.

Practical implications – would focus on actionable steps that organizations and HR professionals can take based on the findings.

Originality/value – lie in the potential to offer insights and practical contributions to the field of human resource management

Key words: evaluation performance process, human resources performance, organizational performance.

Introduction

In any organization the main resource is represented by people, and a good manager must know the people he or she works with, must know not only WHAT can be relied on, but especially WHO. A really delicate problem in the management of an organization is represented by the evaluation of the professional performance of the human resource. Evaluation is part of the managerial function of control and provides a picture of the reality of the organization (Dragomyretska, 2014).

The evaluation of human resources' performance is a crucial part of organizational performance management. In recent years, as organizations constantly seek change and competitive advantage, the key to success lies in performance evaluation (Armstrong, and Baron, 1998). Thus, integrated performance management systems have been developed, most of which are based on competencies.

Organizations, particularly those with private funding, have realized the need to implement a system for evaluating employee performance in order to achieve economic success and a competitive edge. Concurrently, many public institutions have also recognized this need. An important aspect to consider during the evaluation/assessment process is both quantitative (the number of objectives achieved) and qualitative factors (how tasks were carried out, challenges encountered, and how any problems were resolved). Therefore, this paper aims to emphasize the significance of the evaluation process in enhancing employee performance, whether in the public or private sector.

Principles for improving the performance evaluation process

The activity of evaluating human resource performance in organizations is a controversial activity, which gives rise to different opinions and arouses contradictory reactions regarding it. However, it was concluded that the main objectives of the evaluation systems, generally accepted, are: increasing the organization's productivity; establishing the basis for administrative decisions such as promotions, job changes, resignations, and additional training; identifying the objectives and responsibilities of the work place; employee performance evaluation based on these objectives; identifying, for each employee, aspects and improvement areas to increase performance (Emilian et. al, 2003).

Milan Kubr suggests that organizational performance evaluations often focus on numerous criteria and overlook essential aspects (Kubr, 2002). However, this viewpoint is not justified. Evaluations, especially qualitative ones, take into account various factors, including results, traits, and behaviors, thereby offering a comprehensive understanding of employees' work attitude and behavior. Effectively managing this information can help organizations improve their personnel management systems.

Edwards Deming claims that managers focus on creating performance measurement systems that are far too complex and sophisticated to be understood by employees (Manolescu, 2001). Deming, like Kubr, believes that performance evaluation through a performing system should contain representative criteria and be as easy and simple to understand as possible. The two specialists wanted to emphasize that "a complex evaluation system is not necessarily efficient" (Manolescu, 2001). A different vision from that of Deming and Kubr is that of Gerald Cole, who considers evaluation essential, a component of particular importance for ensuring the well-being of an organization. Cole emphasizes the definition of the evaluation as the bilateral discussion between the subordinate and the hierarchical superior to identify the aspects that need to be improved, as well as the elaboration of an action plan (Mathias, Nica, and Rusu, 1997).

Consequently, the performance evaluation must be conducted with utmost attention, as effective management of it can lead to significant benefits for the organization. In this context, certain principles have been outlined to help organizations improve how they carry out the entire performance evaluation process:

- *The first principle* requires that performance evaluation should consider both the individual performance of the employee in their current role and how well they contribute to the organization's goals. Performance and objectives are distinct concepts but should be closely linked throughout the evaluation process.

- *The second principle* focuses on evaluating how well the employee performs the tasks of the job rather than relying on subjective impressions of the evaluator about the employee's work style. The aim is to make the performance analysis objective rather than being based on subjective evaluations of the employee's work style.
- *The third principle* states that the evaluation must be mutually acceptable to both the evaluator and the subject. Both parties must agree that it benefits both the organization and the employee.
- The fourth principle refers to performance evaluation as a means of improving employees' productivity within the organization by better preparing them to produce (Certo, 2002).

The stages of the human resource performance evaluation process

There are several reasons for the development of performance appraisal systems, with their main functions being administrative and employee development. From an administrative standpoint, evaluations provide organizations with valuable information for decision-making processes involving bonuses, salary increases, promotions, and other forms of recognizing and fairly compensating good work (Huțu, and Avasilcăi, 2011). They also enable managers and employees to identify areas with performance deficits, allowing them to develop plans to address the identified issues, as shown in figure 1, which presents the stages of the human resource performance evaluation process.

Creating a solid plan for employee evaluation is a crucial and intricate step in the evaluation process. Managers need to set clear evaluation objectives, establish evaluation criteria and standards, and communicate these to the employees from the beginning. Often, employers make the mistake of assuming that employees understand expectations without clearly communicating and explaining what is required of them. This can lead to misunderstandings and results that fall short of expectations. Additionally, employers need to determine the frequency of evaluations, which are commonly conducted annually in most organizations, and decide who will conduct the evaluations and the methods to be used (Blaga, 2011).

Another crucial step is the evaluation, which involves gathering the initially established data using the predetermined methods. If the initial steps are executed correctly, the data collection process becomes relatively easy (Murphy, 2019).

After collecting the data, the next step involves analyzing the results. The measured results are analyzed and then communicated to the employees. Following this, the necessary measures are taken based on the evaluation. Discussing with employees the areas that need improvement provides an opportunity to guide them toward enhancing individual and organizational performance (Akinbowal, Lourens, and Jinabhai, 2014). Decisions regarding promotions, compensation, additional training, or dismissal are all reliant on performance evaluations. An effective performance appraisal system is essential for meeting legal requirements related to promotions, compensation, and dismissal policies (Katic, and Bevanda, 2019).

The evaluation of the human resource in a Romanian organization

In Romania, there are a multitude of systems and ways to evaluate the human resource in an organization, but practice is faced with evaluation forms imposed by law, standardized with predetermined performance criteria. Romanian legislation, through the Labor Code, grants organizations the right to establish their own individual performance objectives, as well as the evaluation criteria for their achievement. In Law 53 - Labor Code of January 24, 2003, republished and updated, it is stipulated that upon employment the employee must be informed about the criteria for evaluating the employee's professional activity applied at the employer level.

Figure 1. Stages of the human resource performance evaluation process/ system, adaptation after (Mathias, Nica, & Rusu, 1997)

All these must be expressly stipulated in the individual employment contract, but must be distinct from the general evaluation criteria applied at the level of the organization. Thus, the employee's performance objectives are individualized, distinctly designed, personalized for each employee, but the employer is not obliged to include them in the individual employment contract, only those specific at the organization level are included in the individual employment contract, and in the case which is also the case in the collective case, but also in the internal order regulation. The individual employment contract is the result of a negotiation between the two parties, the employee by signing it expresses his agreement regarding the general criteria for evaluating the professional activity.

If, in terms of the legal character that refers to the legal performance of organizations, the Labor Code does not establish clear limits, leaving them to the choice of the employer, in terms of individual performance criteria, the imperative, but also the dispositive character of the

articles clearly emerges, these being essential especially in the case of collective redundancies, where they are the main tie-breaking criterion and only then are the other criteria established by the collective labor agreement or other laws taken into account.

In public organizations in Romania, the appreciation coefficients are established randomly, and the establishment of the general qualification is not given objectively, objectivity being another big problem when it comes to evaluation. Appraisers are sometimes unaware of the organization's performance standards and make a superficial assessment.

Discussion and conclusions

Different countries and cultures have different interpretations of performance evaluation. Human resource management specialists have found that methods of assessing performance that work well in one country and are appreciated by employees may not work in other countries and may be rejected by those employees. This is due to cultural differences and varying value systems. For an evaluation method to be effective, the evaluators must consider the cultural characteristics of the country where the organization is based (Emilian et al., 2003).

Performance evaluation is a fundamental aspect of human resource management. It assesses to what extent employees have fulfilled their tasks and responsibilities within the organization. Without this process, the organization lacks essential data to base its decisions regarding overall performance and the performance of individual components.

Consequently, it is important for a performance evaluation approach to align with the organization's strategic goals, focus on organizational results, and provide constructive feedback for improvement. During periodic reviews, an employee's work performance is assessed to identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. Different organizations utilize performance evaluation results in varying ways, with some using the information for rewarding purposes while others do not fully leverage it. Therefore, performance evaluations are crucial for organizational development.

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